

Preparation and characterization of $\text{Ba}_{0.5}\text{Sr}_{0.5}\text{Co}_{0.8}\text{Fe}_{0.2}\text{O}_{3-\delta}$ for anode application in solid oxide electrolyser cell

Shoroshi Dey, A. Das Sharma and Rajendra N. Basu*

CSIR-Central Glass and Ceramic Research Institute

196, Raja S.C. Mullick Road, Kolkata- 700032, INDIA

E-mail: deyshoroshi@gmail.com

Abstract

Solid oxide electrolyser cell (SOEC) has the great potential for efficient and economical production of hydrogen fuel via high temperature steam electrolysis. It is one of the cleanest methods to produce hydrogen. An SOEC consists of an ion conducting solid electrolyte sandwiched between two porous electrodes. Steam is introduced at the cathode where it is reduced into H_2 , releasing oxide ions which move through the electrolyte to the anode where they combine to form O_2 molecules, releasing electrons. One of the key issues related to the performance of SOEC is the stability of the electrodes under electrolysis conditions (1,2). Therefore, intensive research is being carried out throughout the world to develop stable and highly active electrodes for SOEC application.

Under the present work, $\text{Ba}_{0.5}\text{Sr}_{0.5}\text{Co}_{0.8}\text{Fe}_{0.2}\text{O}_{3-\delta}$ (BSCF) has been prepared for its application as an anode material in SOEC. The material is synthesized through combustion synthesis technique using glycine and /or citric acid as the fuel and corresponding nitrate salts of the metals. Critical process parameters such as fuel to nitrate ratio, metal ion concentration, pH, temperature etc have been optimized. XRD analyses reveal that single phase perovskite of BSCF is obtained at 950°C . Bulk samples have been fabricated through uni-axial compaction of the calcined powder followed by sintering in the range $1250\text{-}1400^\circ\text{C}$. The sintered samples have been characterized through thermal expansion coefficient (TEC) measurements, microstructural analysis and electrical conductivity measurements. Finally, single cell of configuration (BSCF-GDC/YSZ/Ni-YSZ) has been fabricated using tapecasting and screen printing techniques. The performance evaluation of the fabricated single cells (16mm diameter) is currently under progress.

Keywords: Solid oxide electrolyser cell, BSCF, perovskite

References:

Proceedings Of 29th Annual General Meeting Of Materials Research Society Of India And National Symposium On
Advances In Functional And Exotic Materials

1. A. Mahata et al, J. Alloys Compd., 627, (2015), 244-250.
2. A. Mahmood et al, Energy,90(2015), 344-350